

Machine Learning assisted in-device tasks scheduling optimization in context of IoT ecosystems

Mikhail Tishin
Department of Computer Science
University of Nicosia
Nicosia, Cyprus
tishin.m@live.unic.ac.cy

Constandinos X. Mavromoustakis
Department of Computer Science
University of Nicosia
Nicosia, Cyprus
mavromoustakis.c@unic.ac.cy

Jordi Mongay Batalla
Institute of Telecommunications
Warsaw University of
Technology
Warsaw, Poland
jordi.mongay.batalla@pw.edu.pl

George Mastorakis
Department of Management Science
and Technology
Hellenic Mediterranean University
Agios Nikolaos, Crete, Greece
gmastorakis@hmu.gr

Evangelos Markakis
Department of Electrical and
Computer Engineering
Hellenic Mediterranean University
Heraklion, Crete, Greece
emarkakis@hmu.gr

Athina Bourdena
Department of Business Administration
and Tourism
Hellenic Mediterranean University
Heraklion, Crete, Greece
bourdena@hmu.gr

Abstract—Modern IoT and Fog environments are complex and diverse ecosystems that consist of numerous devices. Some of these devices can receive and process offloaded tasks. For such devices to operate at the highest capacity levels, there is a need for mechanisms that could optimize their performance with offloaded tasks. That includes, but is not limited to, such aspects as resource management, workload balancing and scheduling. Unlike local tasks, offloaded ones are not a part of device's environment. Therefore, processing them should not irreparably disrupt a device's functionality. This requires devices to have a mechanism for managing offloaded tasks differently from their local. The current work attempts to research possible ways to optimize in-device execution of offloaded tasks, while reducing detrimental effects to a device's state. To achieve that, the solution involves application of Reinforcement Learning techniques. The work proposes to utilize Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) Actor/Critic method, to allow devices continuously learn optimal scheduling strategies for offloaded tasks. The contribution of this work is in its exploration of the impact machine learning makes on in-device scheduling, application feasibility and the overall execution time optimization of offloaded tasks.

Index Terms—Internet of Things (IoT), task scheduling, Reinforcement Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

The IoT sector nowadays has become a large and integral part of IT industry. The sector itself comprises multiple domains and various IoT configurations. Some of IoT ecosystems

are composed from powerful devices, capable of processing extensive computational workloads. Good examples of such devices are: various high end smart phones, gaming decks, tablets and many similar devices. These devices reflect the ongoing innovation in hardware components manufacturing, including the ones specifically designed for IoT and mobile [1]- [3]. If the processing power of an IoT ecosystem, containing such devices, is properly utilized it can bring various benefits. It can increase degree of independence from the Cloud, making the whole system more autonomous. That can bring improvements in tasks completion time, data privacy, quality of service (QoS) and lower costs of the Cloud services. However, there is a long standing problem - how to orchestrate all the devices in order to utilize their processing power efficiently. Essentially, the problem can be split into 2 parts: workload load-balancing and subsequent in-devices scheduling. There are multiple works related to the problem, some of them are mentioned in Related Work section.

Task scheduling is one of the important aspects responsible for system performance on the software level. It directly affects tasks completion order and time [4], [5]. One of the major efficiency criteria of an IoT ecosystem is the time it takes to process tasks. That is important in the case of offloaded tasks. It includes not only workload distribution between devices, but also the ability to influence its in-devices execution. To

have such an ability is important, in order not to just schedule and execute offloaded tasks, but also to be considerate of a device's state. Offloaded tasks are not a part of a device's OS and ideally should not cause a negative impact, incompatible with device's nominal functionality. For that, it is important to monitor device's local tasks and the state of the system while scheduling offloaded tasks.

Throughout the research it has been realized that there is a couple of main directions to address in-device scheduling considerate of devices state. The first path is to use statistical methods and operating system interfaces. That includes monitoring of local tasks, their CPU consumption and incorporation of these numbers into offloaded tasks scheduling process. The second way is to utilize Machine Learning (ML) methods and to enable system deciding on an optimal scheduling plan. ML has proven to be very helpful in questions of optimization, observation and management of various systems [6]- [10]. There are countless examples of ML application to improve computational systems and to solve general problems. The spectrum of application is wide and covers load balancing, energy consumption, network and performance monitoring.

In context of this work, particularly interesting Reinforcement Learning (RL) [11], [12] for continuously changing environments. This type of ML allows systems/devices to learn their actions based on the previous interactions and states of the environment in a continuous fashion. Another reason to utilize RL in this research is - unlike most of supervised and unsupervised methods, it does not require to collect and store large amount of data to learn. Therefore, can be suitable for devices with a small storage. Although, the amount of data is compensated by the processing power of a device, which has to perform various computations on the fly.

This research focuses on ML assisted in-device scheduling and optimization. It proposes a novel framework, where ML (RL) DDPG [13] finds the best possible permutation of tasks, scheduling policies and priorities. It has potential to reduce offloaded tasks overall execution time, to affect order of completion and to minimize negative effects on a device functionality and its local tasks. Also, it is important to accent that the proposed approach prioritizes utilization of devices processing capabilities over Edge and Cloud. The framework aims to enable device to decide the best way of processing offloaded tasks, depending on device's state at a time.

II. RELATED WORK

Task scheduling in IoT/Fog environments has a series of works. Authors in [14] present a good overview of existing scheduling/offloading solutions for Clod/Fog computing and introduce one of their own. It is an elaborate solution and accounts for such factors as data proximity, device performance and energy consumption. It attempts to optimize tasks completion time, data transmission delay and energy consumption. This work [15], proposes to distinguish workloads by types and to apply an appropriate scheduling strategy for each of the them. For instance, the strategy for heavy workload is based on application of deep reinforcement learning (DRL).

The work is interesting for introducing DRL methods and suggesting adaptive scheduling depending on the workload type. Authors of this work [16] propose blockchain-enabled IoT task scheduling mechanism in a Cloud/Fog environment. The work aims to improve QoS, security of the scheduling system and to minimize fog node energy consumption. However, all of the above works are focused on Fog/Edge nodes and Cloud to offload and schedule tasks, and none considers IoT devices as a computational resource. Many studies consider IoT devices as transmitters of tasks that are being processed by Cloud or Fog environment. This research takes a different perspective and views IoT devices as receivers capable of processing.

The major difference between the related works and the current research is the definition and application of task scheduling. The related works mention scheduling interchangeably with offloading and often represent as a functionality of Edge/Fog servers, rather than in-device. This research views offloading and scheduling functionalities separately and identifies scheduling as strictly in-device inner process. Thus, the main focus of the research is in-device scheduling optimization of offloaded tasks with consideration to device's system state. This can improve the overall execution time of offloaded tasks in some scenarios, resulting in faster tasks completion time and improved QoS. While consideration of device's system state can minimize impact of offloaded tasks on its functionality. Unlike in the related works, the current one aims to investigate performance optimization inside devices, rather than on higher (Cloud/Edge) level. A well configured combination of tasks offloading and in-device scheduling strategies/mechanism, can maximize the overall performance of an IoT ecosystem.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

1. Problem definition

Given an unordered (randomized) set of tasks $T = \{t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, n\}$ where each task i is a loop function and has complexity L_i number of loops. Also given a priority range $Pr = [-20, 99]$, and a set of scheduling policies $Sp = \{FIFO, RR, CFS, IDLE\}$. The agent must find the best possible order for task complexity, scheduling policy and priority to optimize (minimize) the overall execution time, considering the state of device's system, such as local tasks CPU load Sl . Sl scales within the range $1 \leq Sl \leq 10$, where 10 lowest and 1 highest loads. The objective is to train the model to balance scheduling based on the current system load by rewarding decisions that minimize the total execution time without overloading the system.

The system state is one of the most important aspects of scheduling tasks in the current research. Application of different scheduling policies and priorities mostly revolves around the device centrist concept, i.e - how to utilize device's computation resources without exhausting it. It allows to offloaded tasks, foreign to a device, to be processed with great concern to the device's system state. While processing offloaded tasks the state of local tasks and the system load must be monitored. If most of local tasks are in the sleeping or idle state and Sl is low, then offloaded tasks can utilize

the most of computation resources. On the other hand, if local tasks are becoming active, offloaded tasks should gradually release the resources. There is also a case when offloaded tasks, must be suspended to release CPU completely. It is if a device runs critical resource demanding tasks or experiences high Sl throughout certain period of time.

Before discussing the solution model, it is worth of mentioning a few constrains. One, it considers Linux OS, its scheduling policies and the scaling system. Another limitation, the solution excludes from offloaded tasks, real time tasks such as video/audio streaming, or the OS internal tasks of another device. This is due to the overall task's round trip delay. Despite best efforts to optimize the overall completion time of offloaded tasks, such factors as: network requests, offloading and re-execution retry on failure, and in-device execution may take many seconds. Such delay for the time critical tasks is unacceptable. Thus, the offloaded tasks in this research are not time sensitive.

2. Solution Model and Training Environment

The agent accepts parameters L_i , Pr_i , Sp_i and the current Sl before executing a task i . The environment models scheduling of tasks. The output of each execution cycle is the task execution time R_i for each task i . The initial Pr values for each of the tasks are randomly generated within their defined range, depending on the assigned Sp . Afterward, they are adjusted according to the Sl right before executing tasks and re-adjusted by the agent during the training process. If Sl is 1 then (2) resolves to 0, otherwise its proportion fluctuates and ultimately results in the nice value between 0 and -18 for CSF and priority 1 to 90 for FIFO and RR. Sl is the essential part of scaling Sc (1), which provides a smoother transition between priority levels.

$$Sc = Sl \frac{Sl}{10} \quad (1)$$

$$Pr_i = \frac{(E_i - \frac{E_i}{Sc}) * 100}{\sum_{j \in T} E_j} \quad (2)$$

where E_i is estimated execution time of i and $\sum_{j \in T} E_j$ is the total sum of estimated execution times for all offloaded tasks.

Since Sp on Linux have different priority scaling, Pr must be converted to the corresponding ones (3). Essentially, mapping Pr_i values ranging from 1 to 100% to CFS nice value [-20, 0] or to priority [1, 99] in case FIFO and RR. While it can be mapped 1 to 1 for FIFO and RR, the change between CFS nice value scaling is $-100\% / -20 = -5\%$, where 1 nice value = -5% . Thus, it resolves in rounded $Pr_i / -5$.

$$\sum_{i \in T} Pr_i \begin{cases} Sp_i = 0 & Pr_i = \frac{Pr_i}{-5} \\ Sp_i = 1 \vee 2 & Pr_i = f : a \rightarrow b \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Pr sets the initial lower boundary for the agent, from which it is allowed to update priority during the training cycles. In other words, assuming the initial priority of a task is -10 for CFS, the agent is allowed to apply during the training process numbers [-20, -10]. If the state of the system indicates spike

in activity of local tasks, then the scheduling priority is recalibrated to lower values. The agent learns a relation between the Sl and Pr updated values.

The state S at any time is represented by a tuple:

$$S = \{Sp, L, Pr, Sl\}$$

The action A is a tuple $A = (O, T')$, where O represents task execution order, modeled as a permutation of tasks. T' is adjusted task policies for each task, mapped to the set Sp .

The reward R is based on the makespan (total execution time) as (4):

$$R = - \sum_{i=1}^N R_i \quad (4)$$

Negative makespan incentivizes the agent to minimize the total execution time of tasks. Each task's runtime is simulated based on its policy and workload. Execution time R_i is recorded.

3. DDPG Agent

The RL agent uses two neural networks; actor with parameterized policy $\pi_\theta(S)$ to select actions and critic with value function $Q_\phi(S, A)$ to estimate the expected reward of an action.

Critic loss mean squared error - (5) and (6):

$$L_{\text{critic}} = \mathbb{E}[(Q_\phi(S, A) - y)^2] \quad (5)$$

where:

$$y = R + \gamma Q_{\phi'}(S', \pi_{\theta'}(S')) \quad (6)$$

and ϕ' , θ' are target network parameters. Actor loss as - (7):

$$L_{\text{actor}} = -\mathbb{E}[Q_\phi(S, \pi_\theta(S))] \quad (7)$$

4. Training Process

- 1) Sample transitions $(S, A, R, S', \text{done})$ from experience replay.
- 2) Update the critic network using L_{critic} .
- 3) Update the actor network using L_{actor} .
- 4) Periodically update target networks:

$$\phi' \leftarrow \tau\phi + (1 - \tau)\phi', \quad \theta' \leftarrow \tau\theta + (1 - \tau)\theta' \quad (8)$$

The Actor and Critic networks are represented by Feed Forward (Linear) type and essentially operate on matrices. The data in matrices captures the system state, as well as offloaded tasks parameters. With every iteration NN adjusts weights and after executing tasks captures their makespan. Throughout iterations NN is learning the best possible permutation of tasks, scheduling policy and priority, with consideration to the system state, trying to bring R_i to 0 as close as possible. The actor network accepts matrix where each row represents L_i , Pr_i , Sp_i and Sl . An example of calculation is provided below (9) - (13). Given the input matrix X , weight matrix W , and bias vector b :

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 1 & 1 \\ 3 & 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad W = \begin{bmatrix} w_{11} & w_{12} \\ w_{21} & w_{22} \\ w_{31} & w_{32} \end{bmatrix}, \quad b = [b_1 \quad b_2] \quad (9)$$

Fig. 1. DDPG Agent Architecture

The output of the feed forward layer is computed as (10):

$$Y = X \cdot W + b \quad (10)$$

1. Weighted Sum with Bias (11):

$$z = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b \quad (11)$$

2. ReLU Activation Function (12):

$$\text{ReLU}(z) = \max(0, z) \quad (12)$$

The resulting matrix Y is the output of the feed forward layer (13):

$$Y = \begin{bmatrix} y_{11} & y_{12} \\ y_{21} & y_{22} \\ y_{31} & y_{32} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Where y_{ij} represents the computed value for the i -th input and j -th output feature.

The training algorithm provided 1.

Algorithm 1 Episode-based Task Scheduling Algorithm

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1: Input:  $N, env, agent$ 
2: Output: Task execution results and updated agent
3: for  $episode \leftarrow 1$  to  $N$  do
4:   Compute lower bound for  $Pr$  (2) and (3)
5:    $state \leftarrow env.reset()$ 
6:    $done \leftarrow False$ 
7:    $total\_reward \leftarrow 0$ 
8:   while  $\neg done$  do
9:      $(task\_order, policies, priorities) \leftarrow$ 
        $agent.select\_action(state)$ 
10:     $action \leftarrow (task\_order, policies, priorities)$ 
11:     $(next\_state, reward, done, info) \leftarrow$ 
        $env.step(action)$ 
12:     $results \leftarrow info["results"]$ 
13:     $agent.store\_transition(state, action,$ 
        $reward, next\_state, done)$ 
14:     $agent.train()$ 
15:     $total\_reward \leftarrow total\_reward + reward$ 
16:     $state \leftarrow next\_state$ 
17:   end while
18: end for

```

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The tests conducted in the environment with the following properties: Intel Core i7-7700HQ CPU 2.80GHz, 8 cores, 16 GB of RAM and OS - Ubuntu 20.04. PyTorch library is used to create DDPG Actor/Critic and all the necessary neural networks. The testing is performed on a series of tasks of different complexity and under varying system load. The varying system load is achieved by spawning extra tasks outside of agent's scope, in order to create CPU sharing conditions.

The purpose of the experiment is to establish to what extent application of RL affects the completion order and time of offloaded tasks. What role order, scheduling policies and priorities play in that, and what scenarios benefit from that. The proposed solution is compared against standard scheduling such as RR and FIFO.

The experimental results in table I illustrate results for the first 3 tasks out of many. Each entry in the table is the agent training cycle. Each of those 3 tasks is scheduled under CFS. The complexity of the tasks: 0 - 15, 1 - 20, 2 - 25 million loops. The results can be virtually split into 2 parts, one where the system load is 10 and the other where 1. When the system load is 10 the system is nearly idle and the offloaded tasks are having higher priority and larger CPU time slice. As the results, short execution time. However, as soon as the system load drastically changes, by spawning extra tasks, the system load changes to maximum and the execution time surges. The priority of tasks is being re-calibrated to lower.

If the system had median load the execution time would be something average between execution results in I. Collecting results between 2 extreme system states, produces a sharper visual distinction, while states in between are not always that

TABLE I
TASK EXECUTION SUMMARY

System Load	Task Order	Priorities	Execution Results (s)
10	1, 2, 0	-12, -14, -11	3.777, 5.201, 3.274
10	1, 0, 2	-10, -12, -14	4.506, 3.339, 6.247
10	0, 2, 1	-10, -12, -14	4.159, 5.873, 4.606
10	2, 1, 0	-11, -12, -12	6.828, 4.143, 2.793
1	1, 2, 0	16, 18, 16	10.419, 12.687, 7.598
1	2, 1, 0	19, 18, 16	15.243, 11.982, 7.369
1	0, 1, 2	15, 16, 18	7.551, 12.823, 14.602
1	1, 2, 0	17, 19, 15	10.631, 15.231, 7.46

noticeable. The difference in execution times display that there is a correlation between system load, policies and priorities. Although, the tasks order does not affect their total execution time, it is responsible which tasks are being finished and returned earlier to the distributing server. The completion order can be a beneficial factor in some scenarios. For example, if the task distributor, would like to accelerate offloaded tasks estimated execution time on a device. To achieve that, the priority of offloaded tasks can be overridden to surpass local tasks and to have much more of the CPU time.

TABLE II
SCHEDULER COMPARISON: DDPG VS RR VS FIFO

System Load	Scheduler	Priorities	Execution Times (s)
10	DDPG	-12, -14, -11	3.777, 5.201, 3.274
10	RR	1, 1, 1	4.117, 5.332, 4.121
10	FIFO	1, 1, 1	3.801, 5.010, 4.172
1	DDPG	16, 18, 16	10.419, 12.687, 7.598
1	RR	1, 1, 1	4.517, 5.832, 4.921
1	FIFO	1, 1, 1	4.110, 5.210, 4.672

The results in table II provide comparison of first 3 finished offloaded tasks assigned under different system load by a DDPG agent, RR and FIFO. There is a distinct discrepancy between tasks assigned by DDPG and RR, and FIFO. Tasks execution time under RR and FIFO almost remained the same, regardless of the system load, while for the ones assigned under DDPG experienced a drastic change. This change is due to DDPG device's state awareness and dynamic priority adjustment of offloaded tasks. Although, tasks total completion time under FIFO and RR is more preferable, they have intervened and put extra stress on a device during heavy system load. In fact, they have led to CPU starvation condition of the local tasks.

The second part of the experiment is to allow agent to apply different scheduling policies, to identify if there is total execution time optimization. The images Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 represent multiple tasks and multiple training iterations. Where the agent searches an optimal permutation of tasks, priorities and policies. Unlike the previous results, this ones are ambiguous. If to evaluate results under the 6s threshold Fig. 2 has better performance, however, if the evaluation point is below 8s then Fig. 3. Another interesting aspect, is the completion order of tasks by their complexity. In Fig. 2 the highest complexity tasks of 25, and lower of 12 and 15 million loops are processed under 6s, while in Fig. 3 the emphasis is

Fig. 2. Learning Episode 1 - Correlation between complexity, scheduling policy, priority and finishing order

Fig. 3. Learning Episode 2 - Correlation between complexity, scheduling policy, priority and finishing order

on the average complexity of 18 and 20 million loops.

On the other hand, comparing DDPG dynamically assigned scheduling policies against static ones, the most noticeable differences is the CPU sharing. DDPG agent learns to assign policies dynamically with consideration of the system state outlined in III, aiming to prevent CPU starvation caused by offloaded task and trying to improve their total completion time. Statically assigned policies treat both, local and offloaded tasks alike, regardless of the system load, creating a situation where one of the groups experiencing CPU starvation.

Another noticeable aspect is that in the greater context, the execution time gains under mixed scheduling policies may not be the most clear benefit versus resources required to run the agent. The initial requirements to even train the agent start from CPU-1 GHz and RAM 300 - 500 Mb and largely depend on NN depth, replay buffer size and input parameters. Running a DDPG-based RL agent continuously on IoT devices introduces a notable overhead, even on a relatively capable devices, considered in the present work. The constant computations required for learning and scheduling increase CPU usage between 20–40% and battery drain roughly 30+%, which is especially problematic for low-power or mobile devices. Throughout experiments it has been noticed that

weak devices may struggle with the computational and energy demands, making this approach impractical without hardware acceleration or lighter alternatives like statistical methods. Another possible option to avoid constantly running agent is to save and use a pre-trained model, which drastically improves performance. However, that is feasible in a stable or incrementally changing environments, with low variation of tasks and their parameters over time, enough to allow periodic model updates.

To summarize experimental results, perhaps the best outcomes to be noticed are: 1) the completion order of tasks with different estimated execution time, 2) tasks performance management with consideration to device's system state. The policies assigned by the agent would make greater impact if the agent could identify the type of tasks and assign to it a corresponding scheduling policy. The scheduling policies and their effect on the execution time resulted to be the most questionable aspect. Real time scheduling policies, especially FIFO, without well outlined application scenarios, can negatively impact the execution time among offloaded and local tasks, even assigned by the agent. Throughout learning episodes, ultimately, the agent learns the most beneficial scheduling policies and assigns them. In context of the current experiment it is CFS for the most tasks and RR in some cases. The agent stops applying FIFO for the test tasks, after some learning episodes.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The initial research results illustrated that it is possible to use DDPG to learn tasks patterns and to manage offloaded tasks with consideration to the system load. Despite overall minor improvements in offloaded tasks total execution time, it appears to compensate by the number of processed tasks of certain complexity in a specific time frame, by finding a suitable scheduling strategy. Finding suitable tasks order and priority the agent attempts to reduce task execution time in CPU competitive environment, where multiple tasks run for the same resources.

On the other hand, the execution time is not the only criteria. Not overloading device and allowing it process its local tasks is a very important factor in the current research. The initial results indicate that when the system load is increasing the priority of offloaded tasks is decreasing, reducing their CPU time in favor of the local tasks. In general, priority adjustment allows distributor to bypass system load constrain. Passing additional parameters to a device, to force it processing offloaded tasks faster. Of course, as it is pointed in the previous sections, prioritizing offloaded tasks can be detrimental to a device's nominal functionality. Therefore, there can be a set of rules to regulate such behavior. For instance, if in-device offloaded tasks queue has large number of unprocessed tasks with long expired estimated execution time. Which also means, a distributing server has been expecting those tasks for some time. The agent could decide and prioritize those tasks and complete.

However, there is a significant downsides in this approach. The potential agent's computational overhead on devices with weak computational power. As it has been already mentioned in the Experimental Evaluation section, permanently running agent puts a serious strain on a device's resources. In case of weak devices, if possible, it is better to utilize federated learning or statistical methods to achieve the same tasks scheduling, however with much lower computational costs.

Further research should be focused on discovering deeper relations between the system state, task order, priority and policies they are scheduled under. Ideally, the agent should be able to observe the overall state of the system. That includes device energy level, energy consumption by tasks and the working process of various hardware components.

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